

AN ATTITUDE OF TEACHER TRAINEES TOWARDS INFORMATION AND COMMUNICATION TECHNOLOGY

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Introduction

Information and Communication Technologies play a key role in the modern system of education. ICT is the result of man's zeal for achieving utmost sophistication in all fields of his activities. ICT which have such a wide variety of applications are indeed ruling the society. According to UNESCO (2002) Information and Communication technology may be regarded as the combination of Informatics technology with other related technology, specifically communication technology. The various kinds of ICT products available and having relevance to education, such as teleconferencing, email, audio conferencing, television lessons, radio broadcasts interactive radio counseling interactive voice response system, audiocassettes and CDRoms etc. have been used in education for different purposes. According to United Nations report (1999) ICTs cover Internet service provision, telecommunications equipment and services, media and broadcasting, libraries and documentation centers, commercial information providers, network based information services and other related information and communication activities.

ICT is potentially powerful tool for extending opportunities both formal and non-formal education system. Schools should profoundly revise present teaching practices and resources to create effective learning environments and improve lifelong learning skills and habits in their students. ICTs are versatile, and power tools that can help in every purpose and should therefore present in every classroom and library also. ICTs increasing pervade every aspect of life (work learning leisure and health). Because ICTs are excellent tools for information processing the new generation needs to become competent in their use, should acquire the necessary skills, and therefore must have access to computers and networks while at school. Schools are information and knowledge holding institutions. Therefore, ICT should be fundamental information management tool at all levels of an educational system.

Need and significance of the study

Application of technology in teaching – learning for improving academic skills has become the main focus of educational research. The main function of our present ICT educational systems is to promote quality, excellence, providing wider opportunities for teacher education and the development of human resource potential to its fullest extent. Issues such as how, when, and why we should provide future teachers with expertise in the use of technology and the teachers have recognize the importance of students learning how to use technology and have enacted new technology standards that require teachers to integrate the use of technology into the curriculum for every subject. They have seen the real need for students to learn to use technology as a part of their daily lives in order to prepare

themselves for a future field with technology. This made the investigator to study the attitude of teacher trainees towards information and communication technology.

Objectives of the study

- To study the level of attitude of teacher trainees towards ICT.
- To find the difference between male and female teacher trainees attitude towards ICT.
- To compare the attitude of Arts, Science and Commerce teacher trainees towards ICT.
- To compare the attitude of Aided and Unaided teacher trainees towards ICT.

Research question

What is the level of attitude of teacher trainees towards ICT of Pune city?

Research Hypothesis of the study

There is no significant difference between male and female teacher trainees attitude towards ICT.

There is no significant difference between science, arts and commerce teacher trainees attitude towards ICT.

There is no significant difference between Aided and Unaided teacher trainees attitude towards ICT.

Methodology

This study was descriptive nature and normative survey method.

Sample of the study

The sample for the study was selected through purposive Sampling Technique. 3 B.Ed. Colleges (one aided and 2 private unaided) located in Pune City were selected. A total number of 290 B.Ed. Student teachers representing both male and female, subject of studies and institution were considered.

Tools used in the study

In the present study, Attitude towards ICT constructed by investigator was used to collect the required data. The Scale has 30 statements based on 5 point scale 17 statements were positive and 13 statements are negative.

Statistical Analysis of data

Percentage analysis. Mean, Standard Deviation and 't' test were used to assess the significant difference between male and female, and aided and unaided teacher. F-ratio was used to assess the significant difference between Science, Arts and Commerce teacher trainees.

Research question

What is the level of attitude of teacher trainees towards ICT of Pune city?

Table 1: Details of the Level of Attitude among teacher trainees.

Sr. No.	Level of Attitude	F	%
1	Positive	187	64.48
2	Negative	55	18.96
3	Uncertain	48	16.55
Total		290	100

As it is indicated in the table 1 it is found that 64.48% of the teacher trainees showed positive attitude and 18.96% teacher trainees showed uncertain and 16.55% of teacher trainees showed negative attitude towards ICT.

H1: There is no significant difference between male and female teacher trainees attitude towards ICT.

Table 2: Difference between male and female teacher trainees

Gender	Sample size (N)	Mean	Standard deviation	t value	Result
Male	133	48.05	5.589	1.056	Not significant at 0.05 level
Female	157	49.87	4.325		

From the table 2 it is clear that the obtained 't' 1.056 value is not significant at 0.05 level. So the null hypothesis is accepted and it is concluded that there is no significant difference between the male and female teacher trainees in their attitude towards ICT.

H2: There is no significant difference between science, arts and commerce teacher trainee's attitude towards ICT.

Table 3: Subject of study with their Attitude

Subject of study	N	Mean	SD	F-value	Result
Science	85	45.76	3.761	20.154	Significant at 0.01 level
Arts	130	50.34	3.943		
Commerce	75	51.84	4.234		

From the table 3 it is clear that the obtained F value is 20.154 significant at 0.01 level. So that the null hypothesis is rejected. It is concluded that there is significant difference between Science, Arts and Commerce teacher trainees in their attitude towards ICT.

H: There is no significant difference between Aided and Unaided teacher trainees attitude towards ICT.

Table 4. Types of institution with their Attitude towards ICT

Institution	N	Mean	SD	t -value	Result
Aided	95	50.38	5.781	1.081	Not significant at 0.05 level
Unaided	195	47.98	1.742		

The result reveals from table 4 that there is no significance difference between types of institutions at 0.05 level. It indicates that aided and unaided teacher trainees same attitude towards ICT. Hence the null hypotheses accepted.

Conclusion

ICT have brought about a revolution across the world. They have changed the face of society. The present study revealed that the teacher trainees showed positive attitude towards ICT. The study also showed that the importance of ICT in education has been understood by the teacher trainees. Teachers in the present of 21st century must be creative and equip themselves to teach in the era of technology. The uses of information and communication technologies have made an enormous contribution to improving education and to the development of learning theories. Increasing competitiveness, technological change and the reengineering of production and social processes require continuous upgrading of skills and personal growth.

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